

MOTIVATION FACTORS AND ORGANIZATIONAL ROLES: FRAMEWORK FOR STRESS MANAGEMENT AND PRODUCTIVITY AMONG TEACHING PERSONNEL IN LSPU SYSTEM

ELAINE M. FRANCISCO

elaine.francisco@lspu.edu.ph

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus

ABSTRACT

The study delved to ascertain the Motivation Factors and Organizational Roles: Framework for Stress Management and Productivity among Teaching Personnel in LSPU System. The researcher used the descriptive correlational design to describe the data, characteristics used and the population in the study. It was conducted at the Laguna State Polytechnic University randomly selecting 250 teaching personnel. The findings are as follows: The Respondents perception on Motivation Factors is interpreted as “Manifested”. The Respondents perception on the Role of Organization in terms of Role ambiguity, Responsibility, Career Development, are interpreted as “Observed” while the Relationship at Work is interpreted as “Highly Observed”. The Respondents’ adherence to the stress management approaches are all interpreted as “Practiced”. The Respondents’ level of productivity in terms of Research and Extension are interpreted as “Moderately Productive” while Instruction is “Highly Productive”. The regression analyses on motivation factor and role in the organization such as significantly affect the stress management approaches and productivity in terms of Research, Extension and Instruction of the faculty. Based on the findings, the following are concluded: The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents’ motivation and their stress management approaches and productivity is rejected. The hypotheis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents’ observed role of organization and their stress management approaches and productivity is not supported. The hypothesis that the respondents’ profile, singly or in combination, does not affect relationship between the independent and dependent variables is rejected. Thus, the researcher recommends the organization could establish a “stress audit”, leaders should continue to dedicate resources to their current wellness programs. Faculty members take into account the importance of sustained “engaged inquiry”. Mentoring program of the faculty in extension undertakings should be done regularly.

Keywords: Stess; Motivation; Coping Mechanisms; Organization, Program